

Project CHANGES - Spoke 4

D3 – Meta-analysis of the cultural context – v1.0

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Spoke information

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5	Engineering	ENG	Member
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7	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	UNIFE	Affiliated by “convenzione”
8	Università degli Studi di Firenze	UNIFI	Member
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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we present the approach we have developed for analysing the literature of the last few years (2019-2023), aiming at answering two specific research questions, i.e. (1) How have digital applications enriched museum narratives and which areas have they influenced in the last 5 years? (2) How has public fruition been enhanced in the process? We identified 245 relevant bibliographic resources, and the results of a preliminary empirical analysis conducted on them resulted in the identification of three large macro-areas of discussion – i.e. narratives, new museums, and objects. Further results, obtained by applying the PRISMA method for Meta-Analysis of bibliographic literature will be presented in the next deliverable of the Work Package 2, i.e. *D7 - Guidelines and best practices for technology-aided narratives for museums and art collections*.

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1. Introduction

The aim, over the past months, has been to develop an effective tool for analysing the literature of the last few years (2019-2023). The main difficulty encountered was the heterogeneity of our starting points: the domains of the researchers involved in Spoke 4 are varied, ranging from the technical-scientific to the historical-artistic-archaeological, anthropological, communication, education, etc. In order to find a common denominator, a flexible tool was needed to include and merge heterogeneous contributions, without losing sight of the core fact: the need to refine a cultural approach to digitalisation processes in museums, through applicable and, possibly, reproducible cases.

2. Results of a preliminary empirical analysis

Our research began using erratic, non-systematic, bibliographies suggested by different members of the group. Indeed, we had the problem of cross-referencing different disciplinary fields, without neglecting any of them. Between January and August 2023, we made several attempts, but without obtaining appreciable results. The most difficult aspect to tackle was indeed the representativeness of the sample. Subjective interpolation was very strong. Each domain expert inevitably reported important contributions in their own field. Thus, a bibliographic analysis was empirically set up by drawing on a general database (Scopus, <https://www.scopus.com>), using a search string that included the terms "Museum; objects; narrative" in a time span from 2019 to 2023.

The results obtained were 245 distinct bibliographic resources. The most significant essays were chosen on the basis of the titles and contents of the abstracts without using double-blinding for the time being. The decision not to proceed in a double-blind first phase was prompted by the need to deal with general topics without the conditioning of overly precise definitions in order to verify the sustainability of the research.

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Some general lines of interpretation emerged, which we proceeded to identify in three large macro-areas: “narratives”; “new museums”; “objects”.

In the first, the main one, we wanted to include reflections of a more methodological scope that led experts to question the evolution of museum narratives in the contemporary world. Proceeding from some basic assumptions that have helped to define museums as “artificially reconstructed places of memory” (Nora, 1984) “spaces” that progressively take the place of churches where members of a community can gather to celebrate a “new cult” (Pomian, 2022), more recent historiography has questioned the various possibilities for a museum to integrate readers into its narratives, guiding them through the objects on display. A narrative that can go even further, influencing, for instance, the way the reader perceives and evaluates the world in general.

One therefore speaks today of “multiple narratives” (Daybell *et al.*, 2020), constructed and evolved over time: past-oriented, which presents art and other objects chronologically and geographically; the present-oriented where display strategy uses the present as the basis for exhibiting collection objects; postmodern presentation focuses on the difference not between present and past (see the past-oriented presentation), but between the art objects from the past and the history of those objects; the transhistorical one: instead of grouping the collection by period and region/area (see the past-oriented museum), old and recent art or other objects are placed alongside each other (Dekeyzer 2021).

The different forms of narrative are also affected by new sensitivities and historiographical approaches: most of the articles analysed question the need to deconstruct a predominantly Western and colonialist narrative (due to the historical moment in which the main national museums were founded) in order to replace it with a post-colonialist one, which restores a transnational and global vision and the multiplicity of socio-political and cultural constructions.

In addition to these examples of storytelling which aim to work on objects and their material arrangement in museums, there is another one, which has long since been initiated thanks to new technologies and which has undergone a forced acceleration following the Covid19 pandemic episode. This involves the application of new technologies, in particular the digitisation and 3D reconstruction of objects or collections: a “new visualisation” of museums.

Moreover, all scientific articles emphasise the need for an interdisciplinary approach, which is now necessary to foster the development of modern narratives.

If the consideration about narratives proceeds from the analysis of the major national museums - in particular the British Museum - it was possible to identify examples of “new museums” based on single narratives, intended to reflect a national history or a desire to restore a collective memory, with all the “limitations” that this type of memorial narrative presents.

Finally, it is possible to identify an itinerary of reflection linked to the emergence of a “biographical approach to objects” whose focus is on a single object potentially capable of highlighting the “multiple lives” it can tell depending on the narrative approaches chosen. Such a perspective is also useful in demonstrating the need for a multidisciplinary discourse and the comparison with different sources, both paper and bibliographic, in order to avoid “constructing” narratives that tend to prevail over the desire or unintentional risk of specific memorial stories.

Finally, a few general considerations: in the ambit of methodological reflection, the cases studied all move from mainly Anglo-Saxon national museums, a perspective that is perhaps due to the greater attention paid by historiography to the discussion of the imperialist and colonial period. The presence, in fact, of the theme of “de-colonisation” even within museums is predominant: only one of the essays analysed shows, for example, an attempt to propose a gender analysis.

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There is indeed a general tendency to operate in increasingly broad and inclusive contexts. On the contrary, the analysis of what we have defined as “new museums” presents individual, often decentralised cases, which risk in this case to bring the discourse back to a national and exclusionist perspective.

Interesting, because largely present, is the willingness to move in a transdisciplinary perspective, useful for constructing multiple narratives, obviously including new technologies, in a constant dialogue.

At the end of the analysis, we realised that, despite the synthetic elements gathered, we would need a less dispersive and more reliable tool. We thus turned to the PRISMA 2020 method.

3. Methodology

3.1 Tool for meta-analysis

Following preliminary research, which we report on in Section 2, we have thought of using a tool created for meta-analyses in the medical-scientific field, which is one of the most advanced. This is the widely tested PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 method (Page *et al.*, 2021a; Page *et al.*, 2021b). The systematic review has the advantage of combining qualitative and quantitative assessments and of drawing on even mixed databases, such as ours. In fact, the field of Cultural Heritage does not have its own reference databases, but contributions relating to it end up in large international bibliographic repositories (Scopus, Google Scholar, etc.). The PRISMA 2020 Checklist is extremely articulated: while preserving its structure, we have decided to maintain scientific rigour, condensing certain passages proper to medical-scientific domains. Essential steps: Title, Abstract, Introduction, Methods (Identification of new studies via databases and Screening), Results, Discussion.

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3.2. Workflow phases

1. Definition of the research group. The people involved in the study coincided with the members of Work Package (WP) 2 of Spoke 4, including representatives of the majority of the partners involved in the project. In particular, these included scholars from various backgrounds, who nevertheless have decisive expertise in the validation of cross-domain contributions.
2. Definition of the research questions (RQs). We identified two distinct research questions we aimed to answer by running the study, i.e.:
[RQ1] How have digital applications enriched museum narratives and which areas have they influenced in the last 5 years?
[RQ2] How has public fruition been enhanced in the process?
3. Issues arisen: we decided not to use any reference journal and specific databases. Rather, WP2 members will be the keywords to use to search relevant literature, and then strings with keywords will be created. A protocol will be defined and uploaded to an online repository in which questions, sources, and sample definitions will be specified. All the questions, sources, and sample definition will be specified by the members of the WP2 involved. Then, it will be established how the online resources will be retrieved (per abstract and title; per record).
The evaluation of the resources to consider in the study will be double-blind.

3.3. Systematic Review or Scoping Review

At this stage of the project, it is assumed that the emphasis should be on qualitative rather than quantitative data, which is typical for medical-scientific Meta-Analyses. Consequently, the work that will occupy WP 2 from the Autumn 2023 onwards is instead in the area of Systematic Review or Scoping Review.

4. Conclusions

The empirical analysis carried out has proven the feasibility of an analytical path. PRISMA 2020 will make it possible to provide a scientifically meaningful discussion on the contributions of the literature, by placing field research in an up-to-date context of not only technological, but cultural innovation. Such a discussion will be included in the next deliverable of WP2 – i.e. *D7 - Guidelines and best practices for technology-aided narratives for museums and art collections* – that will be submitted by M15 of the project.

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